

Constant Voltage Model of SCIG-Based Variable Speed Wind Power Plant for Load Flow Analysis

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Abstract:

In recent years, the application of variable-speed wind power plants (WPPs) has become more and more popular and surpassed fixed-speed WPPs. This popularity is mainly because variable-speed WPPs are much more efficient in capturing or extracting wind energy than fixed-speed WPPs. Due to its relatively cheaper cost, the use of SCIG (Squirrel Cage Induction Generator)-based variable-speed WPP is currently increasing. This type of WPP is usually equipped with a power electronics converter to obtain a broader range of variable-speed operations. Modeling the power system components

is undoubtedly necessary for performing the system analysis (including load flow analysis). This paper discusses the steady-state model of SCIG-based variable-speed WPP for load flow analysis of electric power distribution systems. The proposed model can be used for SCIG-based variable-speed WPP with voltage control operating mode. The model was developed based on formulas that calculate the turbine mechanical power input and the WPP electrical power output. This paper also presents a case study in which the proposed model is applied to a representative electric power distribution system.

Keywords: *Wind Power Plant, Variable Speed, Load Flow, Power System, SCIG.*

Introduction

Recently, the use of wind energy as an alternative to fossil energy to produce electricity has increased. WPPs can be classified into two large groups: fixed (or near constant) speed WPPs and variable-speed WPPs. Because it is more efficient in extracting wind energy, variable-speed WPPs have begun to replace fixed-speed WPPs.

In fixed-speed WPP, the frequency of the system to which the WPP is connected will determine the rotational speed of the WPP generator. Therefore, the generator speed of this WPP type is only allowed to vary at very narrow intervals (i.e., only around 1 – 2% above synchronous speed). This results in less than optimal use of wind energy. Fixed-speed WPP generally utilizes

SCIG to convert wind energy into electrical power.

Naturally, wind speed constantly changes. On the other hand, in WPP operations, there is a generator rotation speed for a certain wind speed where the power produced by the WPP will be at its maximum. Since the rotational speed of variable-speed WPP can be adjusted to the incoming wind speed, it can capture wind energy optimally. Variable-speed WPP can be accomplished using DFIG (Doubly Fed Induction Generator), PMSG (Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator), or SCIG. However, SCIG-based variable speed hydropower plants have the advantage of relatively lower costs. Furthermore, SCIG-based variable-speed WPP can operate at a reasonably

wide range of rotational speeds, namely 50% below and 10% above synchronous speed.

Modeling the components of the system is very important in studying an electric power system. Load flow analysis is a fundamental analysis in electric power system studies. This analysis is usually carried out to assess the steady-state performance of an electric power system. Several methods have been proposed in WPP modeling for load flow analysis. Some methods are specifically used for fixed-speed WPP (Haque, 2015; Feijoo & Villanueva, 2016; Gianto et al., 2019 & 2021), and others are used for variable-speed WPP (Kumar & Thukaram, 2018; Anirudh & Seshadri, 2021; Gianto, 2021; Elbani & Gianto, 2021). A steady-state model of variable speed WPP based on SCIG for load flow analysis has also been proposed (Elbani & Gianto, 2021). However, the model (Elbani & Gianto, 2021) assumes that the WPP operates in a constant power factor and cannot represent WPP in voltage control operating mode.

This paper discusses a steady-state model of a SCIG-based variable-speed WPP for load flow analysis of electric power distribution systems. The proposed model can be applied for SCIG-based variable-speed WPP in voltage control operating mode. The model is developed based on formulas that calculate the turbine's mechanical power input and the WPP's electrical power output. A validation study is also carried out and discussed in the present paper.

Load Flow Problem Formulation

It can be shown that the load flow problem of an electric power system has the following formulation (Gianto & Khwee, 2021; Gianto, 2021; Elbani & Gianto, 2021):

$$S_{Gi} - S_{Li} - V_i \sum_{j=1}^n Y_{ij}^* V_j^* = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where:

$S_{Gi} = P_{Gi} + jQ_{Gi}$: power generation at i-th bus

$S_{Li} = P_{Li} + jQ_{Li}$: power demand at i-th bus

$V_i = |V_i|e^{j\delta_i}$: voltage at i-th bus

$Y_{ij} = |Y_{ij}|e^{j\theta_{ij}}$: ij-th element of bus admittance matrix

n : number of power system bus

Table 1 summarizes all of the variables (known and unknown) in (1). Some important notes for these variables are as follows: (i) Because the load flow analysis is generally carried out under certain load conditions, the values of P_L and Q_L are known; (ii) The bus admittance matrix \mathbf{Y} is calculated based on network configuration and line impedance/admittance; (iii) The substation bus is usually considered as a reference bus so that the voltage angle at this bus can be assumed to be zero and the voltage magnitude can be specified at a particular value (for example 1.0 pu); (iv) At load buses, P_G and Q_G are all zero because these buses have no power generation sources.

Table 1. Bus Type and Variable

Bus Type	Known Variable	Unnown Variable
Substation (SS)	$P_L, Q_L, Y, V $ and $\angle \delta = 0$	P_G and Q_G
Load	$P_L, Q_L, Y, P_G=Q_G=0$	$ V $ and $\angle \delta$

SCIG-Based WPP

WPP Configuration

Figure 1 shows the basic configuration of a SCIG-based variable speed WPP (Elbani & Gianto, 2021; Akhmatov, 2007; Boldea, 2005). The SCIG rotor is connected to the wind turbine via a gearbox to change the turbine's rotational speed to the higher speed required for the SCIG to generate electrical power. SCIG will then deliver this active power to the power system (power grid) via a power electronic converter

(PEC). This converter (usually back-to-back) consists of a VSC (Voltage Source Converter) or MSC (Machine Side Converter), DC (Direct Current)-link, and VSI (Voltage Source Inverter) or GSC (Grid Side Converter). PEC will isolate

the rotor speed from the system frequency so that the turbine can operate at a wider speed. SCIG-based variable-speed WPP can be operated from 50% below to 10% above synchronous speed (Akhmatov, 2007).

Figure 1. Configuration of SCIG-Based Variable Speed WPP

In Figure 1, P_m is the turbine mechanical power input, P_s and Q_s are the active and reactive power of the SCIG stator, P_g and Q_g are the active and reactive power output of the WPP, V_s is the SCIG stator voltage, and V_g is the WPP terminal voltage. It should be noted that because PEC isolates the SCIG, it cannot be excited from the system or grid. In SCIG-based variable-speed WPP, the reactive power needed for the excitation usually comes from the MSC and is delivered through the stator. Furthermore, in this type of WPP, the GSC is generally set to control the power factor or voltage depending on the selected control strategy. For WPPs that operate in voltage control mode, the reactive power output can be controlled so that voltage regulation can be carried out.

SCIG Equivalent Circuit

Figure 2 shows the steady-state equivalent circuit of a SCIG (Elbani & Gianto, 2021; Akhmatov, 2007; Boldea, 2005). In Figure 2, V_R and I_R are the rotor voltage and current, respectively; V_M and I_M are the magnetic core circuit voltage and current, respectively; and S_S and I_S are the stator

power and current, respectively. Also, in Figure 2, Z_S , Z_R , and Z_M are the impedances of the stator, rotor, and magnetic core circuits, respectively. These impedances are calculated using:

$$\begin{aligned} Z_S &= R_S + jX_S \\ Z_R &= R_R + jX_R \\ Z_M &= jR_c X_m / (R_c + jX_m) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where R_S , R_R , and R_c are the stator, rotor, and magnetic core circuit resistances, respectively; X_S , X_R , and X_m are the stator, rotor, and magnetic core circuit reactances, respectively.

Figure 2. SCIG Equivalent Circuit

Based on Figure 2, the SCIG stator's electrical power and the turbine's mechanical power can be formulated as follows:

$$S_S = V_S I_S^* \quad (3)$$

and:

$$P_m = V_R I_R^* \quad (4)$$

To facilitate the development of WPP mathematical model, turbine mechanical power can be expressed in terms of stator voltage and power as follows (Elbani & Gianto, 2021):

$$P_m = V_S V_S^* Z_{T1} + S_S Z_{T2} + S_S^* Z_{T3} + \frac{S_S S_S^*}{V_S V_S^*} Z_{T4} \quad (5)$$

PEC Equivalent Circuit

Figure 3 shows the PEC model for load flow analysis (Elbani & Gianto, 2021). As explained previously, SCIG delivers power to the system or grid through the PEC system. In Figure 3, it can also be seen that the SCIG is excited from the MSC via the stator terminal. The amount of reactive power required for the excitation is Q_s . In voltage control mode, the GSC controls reactive power and regulates the voltage to a particular value. The amount of reactive power needed for this voltage regulation is Q_g . It should be noted that in Figure 3, V_S is also the MSC voltage, and V_g is also the GSC voltage.

By looking at Figure 3, power loss in the PEC can be determined using:

$$P_{loss,pec} = (V_S - V_g) I_c^* = (1 - \eta_c) P_S \quad (6)$$

where I_c and η_c are PEC current and efficiency, respectively. Since:

$$I_c^* = \frac{P_g}{V_g} = \frac{\eta_c P_S}{V_g} \quad (7)$$

Then, by substituting (7) into (6), the PEC power loss becomes:

$$P_{loss,pec} = (V_S - V_g) \frac{\eta_c P_S}{V_g} = (1 - \eta_c) P_S \quad (8)$$

On using (8), the following relationship can be obtained:

$$V_g = \eta_c V_S \quad (9)$$

Proposed WPP Model

Based on (5) and (9), the proposed steady-state load flow model of SCIG-based variable-speed WPP can be formulated as follows:

$$\frac{V_g V_g^*}{\eta_c^2} Z_{T1} + S_S Z_{T2} + S_S^* Z_{T3} + \frac{\eta_c^2 S_S S_S^*}{V_g V_g^2} Z_{T4} - P_m = 0 \quad (10)$$

Thus, to obtain a solution to the load flow problem of a distribution system containing a SCIG-based variable-speed WPP, (1) and (10) must be solved simultaneously. Table 2 shows all of the variables (known and unknown) in the complete formulation of the load flow problem. It should be noted that the power generation at the WPP bus (S_G) is also the WPP power output (S_g), or:

$$S_G = P_g + jQ_g = \eta_c P_S + jQ_G \quad (11)$$

Figure 3. PEC Equivalent Circuit

Table 2. Bus Type and Variable (System with WPP)

Bus Type	Known Variable	Unknown Variable
Substation (SS)	$P_L, Q_L, Y, V $ and $\delta = 0$	P_G and Q_G
Load	$P_L, Q_L, Y, P_G = Q_G = 0$	$ V $ and δ
WPP	$P_L, Q_L, Y, V = V_g $	$Q_g, \delta = \delta_g, P_s, Q_s$

Case Study

Test System

The application of the proposed model in the load flow analysis of a distribution system will be investigated in this section. The test system used in the study is based on a 12-bus distribution system adopted from (Elbani & Gianto, 2021). This 11 kV system has a total three-phase load of 4,305 MW and 1,215 MVAR. The SCIG-based variable speed WPP is assumed to be connected to bus 12 via a step-up transformer (see Figure 4). Detail of the distribution system and WPP data can be found in (Elbani & Gianto, 2021).

Results and Discussion

Tables 3 – 8 show the system's load flow analysis results. Three values of WPP terminal voltage (i.e., 0.98, 1.0, and 1.02 pu) will be used to investigate the performance of the WPP in

voltage control operation mode. The results in Tables 3, 5, and 7 (columns 4 and 5) show that variations in the WPP voltage almost do not affect the active power output of the WPP. However, these voltage variations have quite an impact on the reactive power output of the WPP. It can be seen that the higher the WPP voltage, the greater the WPP reactive power output, and the WPP can send more reactive power (or the WPP will absorb less reactive power).

Tabel 3. WPP Power ($|V_g| = 0,98$ pu)

P_m (MW)	P_s (MW)	Q_s (MVAR)	P_g (MW)	Q_g (MW)
0.3367	0,3265	-0,0742	0,3102	1,6137
0.5346	0,5187	-0,0898	0,4927	1,3085
0.7980	0,7706	-0,1210	0,7321	0,9434
1.3362	1,2724	-0,2202	1,2088	0,3087
1.5586	1,4748	-0,2748	1,4011	0,0809
2.0745	1,9333	-0,4312	1,8367	-0,3872
2.6933	2,4631	-0,6738	2,3400	-0,8585
3.4243	3,0598	-1,0400	2,9068	-1,3163

Tables 3, 5, and 7 (columns 2 and 3) also show that with the increase in turbine power, the active power of the SCIG stator also increases. However, because of the power losses in the SCIG, this stator active power will be slightly smaller than the turbine power. Meanwhile, the value of the SCIG stator reactive power is always negative, which means that the SCIG absorbs

reactive power. SCIG needs this reactive power to produce a magnetic field for magnetization. It should also be noted that the greater the stator's

active power, the higher the reactive power required for the magnetization.

Figure 4. Test System

Tabel 4. SS Output and Line Losses ($|V_g| = 0,98$ pu)

P_m (MW)	SS Output		Line Losses	
	MW	MVAR	MW	MVAR
0.3367	4,4774	-0,1251	0,4826	0,2735
0.5346	4,1897	0,1175	0,3775	0,2111
0.7980	3,8495	0,4288	0,2766	0,1572
1.3362	3,2693	1,0302	0,1731	0,1240
1.5586	3,0649	1,2673	0,1610	0,1331
2.0745	2,6525	1,7946	0,1841	0,1924
2.6933	2,2488	2,3900	0,2838	0,3165
3.4243	1,8706	3,0460	0,4724	0,5147

Tabel 5. WPP Power ($|V_g| = 1,00$ pu)

P_m (MW)	P_s (MW)	Q_s (MVAR)	P_g (MW)	Q_g (MW)
0.3367	0,3264	-0,0764	0,3101	2,0601
0.5346	0,5188	-0,0914	0,4928	1,7319
0.7980	0,7712	-0,1214	0,7326	1,3412
1.3362	1,2743	-0,2170	1,2106	0,6654
1.5586	1,4774	-0,2695	1,4036	0,4235
2.0745	1,9381	-0,4201	1,8412	-0,0730
2.6933	2,4712	-0,6536	2,3477	-0,5730
3.4243	3,0733	-1,0051	2,9196	-1,0597

From the load flow analysis results, another interesting thing that can be observed is the reduction in substation active power output when the WPP power is increased (see Tables 4, 6, and 8). A decrease in active power supply from

the substation can occur because the WPP can supply some of the system load.

Tabel 6. SS Output and Line Losses ($|V_g| = 1,00$ pu)

P_m (MW)	SS Output		Line Losses	
	MW	MVAR	MW	MVAR
0.3367	4,5596	-0,4939	0,5646	0,3512
0.5346	4,2486	-0,2467	0,4365	0,2702
0.7980	3,8827	0,0698	0,3103	0,1960
1.3362	3,2617	0,6803	0,1673	0,1307
1.5586	3,0434	0,9206	0,1420	0,1291
2.0745	2,6031	1,4553	0,1393	0,1673
2.6933	2,1717	2,0593	0,2144	0,2713
3.4243	1,7658	2,7257	0,3804	0,4510

Tabel 7. WPP Power ($|V_g| = 1,02$ pu)

P_m (MW)	P_s (MW)	Q_s (MVAR)	P_g (MW)	Q_g (MW)
0.3367	0,3263	-0,0787	0,3099	2,5467
0.5346	0,5189	-0,0931	0,4929	2,1913
0.7980	0,7717	-0,1220	0,7331	1,7711
1.3362	1,2761	-0,2141	1,2123	1,0492
1.5586	1,4799	-0,2468	1,4059	0,7917
2.0745	1,9425	-0,4099	1,8454	0,2644
2.6933	2,4789	-0,6347	2,3549	-0,2663
3.4243	3,0859	-0,9727	2,9316	-0,7835

Tabel 8. SS Output and Line Losses
($|V_g| = 1,02 \text{ pu}$)

P_m (MW)	SS Output		Line Losses	
	MW	MVAR	MW	MVAR
0.3367	4,6755	-0,8762	0,6804	0,4555
0.5346	4,3371	-0,6236	0,5250	0,3527
0.7980	3,9414	-0,3012	0,3695	0,2549
1.3362	3,2744	0,3192	0,1817	0,1534
1.5586	3,0408	0,5631	0,1417	0,1399
2.0745	2,5702	1,1055	0,1106	0,1549
2.6933	2,1089	1,7182	0,1589	0,2370
3.4243	1,6737	2,3951	0,3003	0,37966

Conclusion

In this paper, a SCIG-based variable speed WPP steady-state model in voltage control mode for load flow analysis of electric power distribution systems has been proposed. The model has been developed based on formulas that calculate the turbine mechanical power input and the WPP electrical power output. The integration of the proposed model in load flow analysis has also been discussed and presented in this paper. Test results show that the proposed model can represent SCIG-based variable speed WPP operating in voltage control modes.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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